

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

TRANSLATION PROBLEMS OF NIZAMI GANJAVI'S WORKS

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Abstract

The article first discusses the stages of the art of translation, the history of the development of translation. Thus, translation helped to form world culture, way of thinking, and ideology in cultural and historical periods, and it already existed orally before the emergence of writing culture. In Azerbaijan, the first examples of translations date back to the 14th century. The first example of translation in our native language belongs to the 14th century. It is regrettable to say that the works of a genius like Nizami Ganjavi, who opened a bright page in the classical literature of Azerbaijan, started to be studied only from the 20th century.

As we know, translating of great poet's works into our language has been during the Soviet period. The poet's first poem "Sirler khezinesi" (The Treasury of Mysteries) was translated from the scientific-critical text compiled by A. Alizade, under the guidance of Y. Bertels. It can be said without hesitation that along with errors in the translations, there are also distortions that correspond to the requirements of the Soviet ideology. Although all the classical authors of world literature have been translated many times into different languages, the works of a great poet like Nizami were translated into our language only during the Soviet period. In all these translations, the poet's ideology, his perception of the world, his philosophical views are inversely proportional to the truth. It is clear that this was done under the dictates of Soviet thinking. According to the requirements of the time, they did not present us a poet like Nizami as he was, who lived a pious and ascetic life. None of these translations, made at different times, are satisfactory. In some translations, complex characters have been shortened and translated into our language with the translator's personal additions and approach.

Keywords: translation, literature, classical, Nizami, different languages.

INTRODUCTION:

Since the creation of the world, it has happened murders and corruptions that started with the crime committed by the sons of Adam (pbuh), continuous wars and centuries-long conflicts, countless invasions and aggressions. If looking through the history, there will not find a nation of the world that has not been invaded and attacked by other nations. Alexander the Great conquered large areas of Asia and spread the Greek language and Hellenistic culture in the Iranian Empire. However, this could not prevent the spread of Homer's poems, Aristotle's philosophy, religious, moral, social and political views of Avesta, nor Firdowsi's epic among these peoples. It means that people have always needed a means of communication to understand each other. As one of the oldest human activities, translation has played the role of a bridge between peoples, nations, and societies. Through this bridge, people got to know each other and became familiar with each other's culture and history. "Translation is an act that fundamentally ensures that nations come closer to each other, become friends, benefit from each other's development and cooperate with each other" (7;1). Translation helped the formation of world culture, way of thinking, and ideology in cultural-historical periods, and existed orally even before the emergence of written culture. "If the history of oral translation is the same age as the history of the creation of society, the activity of written translation is also the same age as the emergence of writing" (9;108).

The history of translation in the East began with the emergence of the Islamic religion. With the spread of Muslim culture in the Near and Middle East, Iran,

West India, and North Africa from the 7th century, a new culture began to be formed in this area with the participation of many non-Arab peoples - Persians, Syrians, Greeks, and Jews. It was this culture that performed a kind of mediating mission between Eastern and Western cultures. Over the years, every nation and society that was subjected to the Arab invasion felt that they were a part of this culture. The reason for this is that the Arabic language is the language of the Islamic religion - the Quran. It was the Quran that formed the "Islamic culture" by bringing close cultures together. "A single new culture continued the traditions of Hellenism to some extent under completely new conditions, and the Arabic language played an important role as well as the Greek language". (19;10)

The 8th century can be considered the flourishing period of the art of translation. It was from this period that dictionaries in the Arabic language began to be compiled. This has created a fertile ground for the activation of translation activity. Unfortunately, there is no reliable information about the existence of bilingual or multilingual dictionaries. However, the existence of Arabic-Persian and Arabic-Greek dictionaries is a fact. The existence of dictionaries already showed the intensity of exchange of ideas. This also began with the translation of the holy book into other languages. Thus, in Spain, the Quran was translated into Latin and Hebrew, and in the 12th century, at the initiative of abbot Peter, the holy book was translated into Latin by three Spaniards. (It was translated into Latin by T. Bibliander in Switzerland in 1543, into Italian in 1547, and the first translation into French was made by A. Du Ryer in 1649.) Just as the Quran was translated from Arabic

into other languages, from the 8th century also The Bible, which is considered a holy book of Christians, was also translated into Arabic. Thus, it can be said that in the first development period of the history of translation, both translations into and from the Arabic language had a great role. It was not possible to determine the date of the first written translation in Arabic. As a reason for this, Filtishinsky shows the incompleteness of the work on the original text in the history of medieval Arabic literature, and the majority of manuscripts were not involved in scientific research (19; 11).

From the 7th century onwards, the influence of the Islamic culture pre-determined the cultural development of Iran for many centuries and endowed the Iranian culture different characteristics from the classical Arab-Muslim culture. It is also necessary to mention that the Arab culture could not completely infect the Iranian culture. Thus, Iran relied on its rich ancient culture. It would not be wrong to say that the first translation work in Iran began with the transformation of Avesta into Pahlavi. In addition, although there are translations of Buddhist literature from Sanskrit into the ancient Pahlavi language, no detailed information is found about it except for small notes. During the Sassanid era, who became the main promoters of the art of translation, besides translations from Greek and Latin, literature related to various sciences was also translated.

The first examples of translations in Azerbaijan belong to the 14th century. The first examples of translations in our native language also belong to this century. The Azerbaijani poet Mustafa Zarir, who lived in the 14th century, translated Ibn Ishaq's "Kitabu-siratur-Rasulullah" into our language under the name "Siratun-Nabi or Siyar" in both prose and poetry.

Speaking of translation works, it should be noted that Ibn Bazzaz Ardabilli's book titled "Safvatus-Safa" written in Persian was translated into Turkish by Muhammad bin Huseyn Katib Nishati in 1543 under the name "Sheikh Safi". In addition, the translation of M. Shabustari's work "Gulshani-raz" by Sheikh Alvan Shirazi also belongs to the 14th century. "If considering that our classical pearls of art are written in Arabic or Persian, it is very little to clarify only by single research, the history of existence of our art in the texts of English oriental studies, which are mostly translated as Arabic or Persian examples." (13;12)

The work of translation, which began in Azerbaijan in the 14th century, matured with the translation of religious works, tazkira and texts of various contents, and rose to the level of art in the 19th century. Starting from the 19th century, such works as "Kalila and Dimna", Sadi's "Bustan", "Gulistan", Ferdowsi's "Shahnama", etc. have been translated into our language. In the words of Kamal Abdulla, translation is "not a manifestation of one culture, but a point where at least two cultures meet, it is a real multicultural reality". It is regrettable to say that the works of a genius like Nizami Ganjavi, who opened a bright page in the classical literature of Azerbaijan, have only begun to be studied since the 20th century.

METHODS AND MATERIALS:

European scholars began to study the poet after the authors of tazkira (M. Ovfi, A. Jami, L. Azer, D. Samargandi, etc.) who were the first to inform about Nizami Ganjavi, who being the key to Azerbaijan's treasure full of wisdom, who saying that poetry ended with himself. European orientalists have not been able to study Nizami enough, just as the tazkirists did not talk about Nizami's philosophy, his artistry, and his poetic talent. Thus, "of course, neither the medieval tazkirists nor the predecessors of the poet set themselves the goal of discovering and exploring the inner meaning of Nizami's artistry." (14;189). Scholars such as Darmstetter, Ete, Jacob, Brown, Miller, Barbier de Maynard, Pizzi J. did not involve Nizami in research as a special subject, they did not conduct in-depth research on this poet who has great power in his works. Among the European orientalists, the research conducted by the Czech scientist Ripka on Nizami Ganjavi's work is more important. Thus, Azada Rustamova writes about the researches of European researchers in her monograph entitled "Nizami Ganjavi": "...But the poet's art is not particularly highlighted in these works. It is limited to note the poetic richness of Nizami's poetry, only in separate cases the shape characteristics, size, and shades of meaning of some words and phrases etc. are studied from the poet's heritage". (14;190-191)

In the East, one of the notable works is the work of Indian scientist Shibli Nemani "Sherul-Ajam". In this work, the author talked about Nizami's poem "Iskandarnama", studied Nizami's artistry from many aspects, and put forward "thoughts about the style of Nizami's poetry, genre features, the power of artistic description, psychological and emotional scenes etc., which are still fresh from the point of view of literary studies". (14;191)

Vahid Dastgardi is one of the scholars who has an undeniable contribution to Nizami research. For the first time in 1313/1934, he prepared a perfect scientific-critical text of Nizami's "Khamsa". The scientific-critical text compiled by the respected scientist emerged as a result of the comparison of thirty manuscripts. V. Dastgardi compiled a dictionary by writing comments on complex ideas and verses in Nizami's works. It should also be noted that the copy published by Vahid Dastgardi is considered one of the most reliable copies.

The study of the Nizami heritage in Russia is connected with the name of A. Krymsky. Thus, Nizami's creativity was first involved in research by him. In his work "History of Iran, its literature and dervish theosophy" written in 1900, Nizami Ganjavi's life and work were included, and some examples of his works were translated into Russian.

The name of Y.E. Bertels, who devoted most of his life to the study of Nizami's creative work and the heritage of the genius poet, should be specially mentioned. Y.E. Bertels was able to revive the general landscape of the literary environment of the period in which the poet lived, and to obtain important scientific results by correctly evaluating the practice of Nizami's poetics and philosophy. He even disagreed with V. Dastgerdi's comments at some points and expressed his opinion.

In 1939, on the eve of Nizami Ganjavi's 800th anniversary, the scientific-critical text and translation of the great poet's works into our native language was held at the state level. Although the beginning of the Great Patriotic War delayed this work, after the war, in 1947, the poet's 800th anniversary was celebrated.

F. Kocherli, who said that in the past centuries, "there were few eloquent, fluent smooth-tongued poets in the world" like Nizami (8;100), saying that "it is not fair that his magical words were translated into European languages and spread widely, while we read them in our own language and are deprived of delight" (8;102) brought the existence of the problem to the forefront.

As we know, translating of great poet's works into our language has been during the Soviet period. The poet's first poem "Sirlər khezinesi" (The Treasury of Mysteries) was translated from the scientific-critical text compiled by A. Alizade, under the guidance of Y. Bertels. It can be said without hesitation that along with errors in the translations, there are also distortions that correspond to the requirements of the Soviet ideology. Although all the classical authors of world literature have been translated many times into different languages, the works of a great poet like Nizami were translated into our language only during the Soviet period. In all these translations, the poet's ideology, his perception of the world, his philosophical views are inversely proportional to the truth. It is clear that this was done under the dictates of Soviet thinking. According to the requirements of the time, they did not present us a poet like Nizami as he was, who lived a pious and ascetic life. None of these translations, made at different times, are satisfactory. In some translations, complex characters have been shortened and translated into our language with the translator's personal additions and approach. "Among the translations of this poem, there are those that you can't help but feel embarrassed while reading it, and it is not possible to call it a translation, a quote, or a poem". (15;7)

However, even though we have been freed from the Soviet yoke for more than 30 years, no fundamental research work has been conducted on Nizami. Presenting this genius, whose ethnicity is proven to be of Turkish origin, is still presented as a Persian poet should ensure that this work is done faster. Nizami should be investigated, involved in research not only in "Nizami's year" but in all years. In order to perceive and understand Nizami as he is, the poet's creative work must be re-examined and translated. It should also be noted that it is advisable to make translations directly from the original. As philology is related to stylistics, theory of translation is closely related to the organic combination of linguistic and literary methods. When translating from the original text, it should not be forgotten that the functional diversity of bilingualism stands in front of the translator. Translation is a complex and engaging process that requires the ability to feel and understand the diversity of the linguistic world. Making the translation directly from the original text is a guarantee of the value of the work done. However, none of Nizami's poems were translated directly from the original text. Therefore, these translations are controversial. During

the preparation period for the 800th anniversary of the great poet, some points related to the translation were reflected in a document prepared in Russian by the People's Commissariat of Internal Affairs of the Azerbaijan SSR with the glyph "Top Secret". So, we present that document below:

"On preparations for the anniversary of the Azerbaijani poet Nizami Ganjavi"

It is intended to hold an anniversary related to the 800th anniversary of the birth of the great Azerbaijani poet Nizami Ganjavi (Ganja, 941 in today's Kirovabad city) in 1941.

Despite the enormous political and serious scientific significance of Nizami Ganjavi's anniversary, a number of important shortcomings and errors are observed in the work done in connection with the preparation for the anniversary and the publication of the poet's works in the Azerbaijani language.

The complete text of the Nizami Ganjavi's heritage is translated based on the 7-volume collection prepared by a compiler named Vahidi Dasti Kardi1 and published by "Armagan" [magazine] editorial office in Tehran.

This publication is not prepared scientifically and contains numerous errors and distortions. In addition, all those books have a note on the cover that says "All rights belong to the compiler", that is, scientific research or translation without the appropriate consent of the compiler as if has been declared inviolable.

The use of Dastgardi's those collections for translations, first of all, will create confusion in the field of correct understanding of Nizami Ganjavi's creative work, because their compiler cannot be fully trusted; and secondly, it could cause a political scandal, as under existing "copyright", Kardi could sue through his government for the use of his publication and demand royalties of several million rubles. (If Nizami Ganjavi's works are published in all close republics based on literal translations into the Azerbaijani language, the total circulation is taken into account).

Ancient manuscripts and separate editions of Nizami Ganjavi's [works] have existed for a long time. Some of these valuable manuscripts and publications (both originals and photocopies purchased from abroad in exchange for foreign currency) are stored in the Azerbaijan Branch of the [USSR] Academy of Sciences, as well as in other scientific institutions in the cities of Moscow and Leningrad. In order to compile a complete, correct and scientific text of Nizami Ganjavi's works, the comparison of those manuscripts and editions is required, but this is clearly ignored. This work is supposed to be done after the completion of literal translations based on the ready texts of the Kardi edition, which will necessarily be accompanied by numerous changes and corrections, and it will lead to spending additional money and time to change both literal, and poetic translations that have already been done to a large extent.

There is no strong scientific-political and financial control over the work of preparation for the anniversary, monopolization and obvious profit-seeking

tendencies, which turned into speculation with the creative work of Nizami Ganjavi for the sake of personal gain, are manifested.

In the Institute [Literature and Language] named after Nizami (deputy director - Dadashzade Arif, neutral, order-bearer; head of the Department of Literature - Arasli Hamid, neutral) the literal translation and editing work has been mainly divided between 4 people, while for this purpose had to be created a brigade-collective consisting of employees who know the language and spirit of the Nizami period. As if this were not enough, during the distribution, the knowledge of the Persian language, abilities and scientific qualifications of those employees, as well as the workload, were not taken into account. So, as a source of easy income, Arasli Hamid has undertaken the editing of three poems, totaling at least 60,000 verses, while he cannot read Persian properly.

The same situation is observed with Abdulla Shaig, Ibrahim Tahir, Rzaguluzade etc. translators and editors.

The tendency to hinder (at least through the media), the involvement of competent intellectuals, the broad circles of Nizami Ganjavi's fans and admirers in this work is also evident. So, for example, according to the available information, the neutral Rafili Mikayil, the responsible secretary of the Government Commission, who has a poor understanding of issues related to Nizami Ganjavi's creative work, sometimes stifles people's initiative, ignores useful suggestions and often even good ideas. He has earned a bad reputation among some experts, and they say that "as long as Mikayil Rafili's "supervision" lasts, they will not write anything".

Many translators made mistakes in the translations, distorted the ideas, and did not accurately convey the content of individual verses due to lack of knowledge of the Persian language etc. at the proper level and incompetence. The signs of "khaltura" (pot-boiler) and primitiveness are evident here.

A number of workers (Babayev Fazil - member of the CP, Aliyev Mubariz - neutral) have extensive summaries containing facts showing the extent of errors and distortions in the translations of Nizami Ganjavi's works.

The low quality of work, especially in poetic translations, is clearly visible. With the exception of the poet Samad Vurgun's and partially Mammad Rahim's, the remaining poetic translations are of low quality and, according to the information we have, are nothing more than caricatures to Nizami Ganjavi's works. There is no artistry or magnificence in them, the genius and greatness of Nizami Ganjavi is not felt. The great classical and genius poet Nizami Ganjavi often gives the worst and ordinary prose effect in these translations (for example, the poems "Iskandernama", "Haft Peykar", etc.).

Huseynov Heydar, director of the Institute [Literature and Language] named after Nizami, member of the CP, was informed about most of the listed facts, but he did not inform the governing bodies about it.

Azerbaijan SSR People's Commissar of Internal Affairs, State Security Major (Yemelyanov)16

August 17, 1939, Baku.

Executive: Mustafayev!" (12;10)

From the content of the reference, it is understood that it is important to re-examine and translate Nizami's creative work, and that the translation made is not satisfactory. The poet's first work "The Treasury of Mysteries" was translated by Suleyman Rustam, Abbasali Sarovlu, Khalilrza Ulutürk. The text prepared by R. Aliyev, who made a philological translation of this masnavi based on two ancient manuscripts, is more reliable and authoritative. By the way, let's also note that the most complex of Nizami Ganjavi's works is the "The Treasury of Mysteries" written in 1174-1175. That is why many researchers have tried to interpret this work.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

It should be noted that many subtleties should be taken into account when translating any classical literature. The spirit of the poet who translating Nizami's heritage should be close to the spirit of classical literature. It is meaningless to translate without knowing these points and without considering these nuances. Because precisely these subtle points contain the depth of Nizami's philosophy. It should not be forgotten during translation that the language of poetry is very different from ordinary language. The artistic-aesthetic value of the Nizami's word indicates the richness of its art world.

With the special arrangement of words in each line, the wordplay creates a beautiful harmony by enhancing the value of language of the poem. Nizami, as a symbolist poet, narrated all his life observations by the language of poetry, and made sufficient use of metaphors and similes. Nizami created a unique style, with this style he brought innovation to literature. He was able to distinguish his writing by the originality of meaning and arrangement of words. As the poet himself says about this:

عاریت کس نیپذیرفته ام
آنچه دلم گفت بگو گفته ام
شعبده تازه برانگیختم

هیکلی از قالب نو دوخته ام(22;36)

Heç kimdən mən hələ bərc almamışam,
Ürəyim nə istəyib onu da demişəm.
Yeni bir şəbədə qurmuşam,
Təzə qəlibdə yeni heykəl yaratmışam.

(lit: I haven't borrowed anything from anyone yet.

I said what my heart wanted.

I have set up a new branch,

I have created a new sculpture in a new mold.)

Nizami's poem is at the peak of the art of poetry both in terms of form and meaning. His powerful imagination has enriched his poetry even more. The peculiarity of the Nizami language is that it uses new expressions and chooses unusual compositions. When translating the works of this genius poet, simile, metaphor, irony, sarcasm, pun, touzi, tarsi, etc. word subtleties must be taken into account. It is difficult to translate his works without knowing these art forms. For example, we show a verse from Nizami's poem "Leyli and Majnun" below:

خواهم که به یاد عشق مجنون
رانی سخنی چو در مکنون (21;25)

In these verses, the words *majnun* and *meknun* are *tajnisi-mutarraf*, that is, they are half-pun. Puns are words in poetry that have the same in form but different in meanings. (10:189) Below we give Samad Vurgun's translation into our language:

İstəyirəm ki, Məcnun eşqi xatirinə,
Sədəfdəki inci kimi bir söz deyəsən. (3;34)

(lit: I want you to say a word like a pearl in a shell for the sake of Majnun's love)

As it can be seen, during the translation, the pun has lost, and the wonderfulness of the verse has not been preserved. It means that classical text translation requires more attention. "In other words, if the means of artistic expression such as simile, metaphor, irony etc. are not preserved in the translation of the poem, it is impossible to talk about its artistic features." (15;5)

By the way, it should be noted that classical texts are rich in religious terms, words taken from the Quran and hadiths. The works of Nizami, who has a deep faith in God and is extremely attached to him, who recognizes monotheism as the basis of human freedom, are rich in the Quran and hadiths, which he used.

The poet who preached monotheism the most began his works with monotheism, prophecy, and imamate. Doctor Nizami sometimes indirectly and sometimes directly pointed to any Quran verse. For example, the introduction to the work of "The Treasury of Mysteries" says:

اول و آخر به وجود و صفات
هست کن و نیست کن کاینات (22;3)

Əvvəl də, axır da məxsusdur ona
Var edib yox edən də odur.
(lit: The first and the last also belongs to him,
He is the one who creates and destroys)

Here, the third verse of the "Hadid" surah of the Quran is indicated.

«هُوَ الْأَوَّلُ وَالْآخِرُ وَالظَّاهِرُ وَالْبَاطِنُ وَهُوَ بِكُلِّ شَيْءٍ عَلِيمٌ»
that is, "He is the First and the Last, and the Manifest and the Hidden". (11;57)

Below is another example:

هستی تو صورت و پیوند نی
تو بکس و کس بتو مانند نی (22;7)

Varlığının nə siması, var nə də peyvəndi.
Sənə oxşayan da yox, sən də heç kimə
oxşamassan.

(lit: His presence has no face, no vaccine.
There is no one like you, and you are like no one)

Here Nizami Ganjavi pointed to the verse «لَمْ يَلِدْ» (11;112). «وَلَمْ يُولَدْ وَلَمْ يَكُنْ لَهُ كُفُوًا أَحَدٌ»

In praise of the Prophet, he says:

ره به تو یابند و تو ره ده نه ای
مهتر ده خود تو و در ده نه ای. (22,22)

Sənə yol tapırlar, amma sən yol vermirsən,
Sən kənddə olmasan da, amma kətxudasan.

(lit: They find a way for you, but you don't give way,
Although you are not in the village, but you are a head of village).

It is very difficult to understand something when reading a verse. Because in order for the common reader to understand what Nizami is referring to, he needs to be aware of many points. Thus, the poet quoted the Quran verse and showed the prophet as the cause of people coming to the right path. But only God is the owner of the straight path. The poet said this by referring to the 56th verse of "Al-Qasas" surah of Quran. So this verse says:

{ إِنْكَ لَا تَهْدِي مَنْ أَحْبَبْتَ وَلَكِنَّ اللَّهَ يَهْدِي مَنْ يَشَاءُ وَهُوَ أَعْلَمُ
بِالْمُهْتَدِينَ }

"You surely cannot guide whoever you like, but it is Allah Who guides whoever He wills, and He knows best who are "fit to be" guided." (11;56)

When the poet said "ره ده" here, he did not mean guidance. To show the way is the main mission of the Prophet. Achieving the desired is God's work. Only God shines the light of guidance on people's hearts.

In each verse of Nizami Ganjavi, each science finds its inspiration. Without familiarity with Islamic philosophy, it is very difficult to understand Nizami. For example, we give an example from "The Treasury of Mysteries":

سایه نداری تو که نور مہی
رو تو که خود سایه نور اللہی
چار علم رکن مسلمانیت

پنج دعا نوبت سلطانت (22;23)

Kölgən yoxdur, sən bir ay kimisən,
Sən özün ilahi nurun kölgəsisən.
Müsalmanlığın dörd ələmisən,
Beş duanın səltənətisən.
(lit: You don't have shadow, you are like a moon,
You yourself are the shadow of the divine light.
You are the four flags of Islam,
You are the kingdom of five prayers.)

"چار علم" - Here, when the poet says 4 flags, he means prayer, fasting, almsgiving and pilgrimage, and when he says five prayers, he means five times prayer. Quran() In the following lines, it is pointed out to the verse directly.

کیست در این دیرگه دیر پای
کو لمن الملک زند جز خدای (22;3)

Here the poet pointed to the 16th verse of Surah Ghafir.

«لَمَنْ الْمَلِكُ الْيَوْمَ لِلَّهِ الْوَاحِدِ الْقَهَّارِ» Allah will ask, "Who does all authority belong to this day?" (11;40) In Rustam Aliyev's translation, these lines sound like this:

Bu qoca, əbədi dünyada
Tanrıdan başqa kim deyə bilər ki, "Bu varlıq kimindir?" (2;17)

(lit: In this old, eternal world, who but God can say, "Whose is this being?")

And, in Khalil Rza Ulutürk's translation, it's said so:

Tapıların cahanda onunla bəhs eyləyən?
Varmı ondan savayı "bu mülk mənimdir" deyən.
(4;24)

(lit: Is there anyone in the world who bets with him? Is there anyone who says "this property is mine" except him).

In the translation belonged to M.Zaki, "المن الملك" in this verse has been kept as it is. By the way, it should be noted that the errors and misunderstandings in the translations also attract attention. Below we give a verse from the "The Treasury of Mysteries":

کی شدی آن سنگ مفرح گرای
گر نشدی در شکن و لعل سای (22;23)

And, now we present the translation of these verses by different authors.

Ta ki o daş oldu müfərrih gəzən,
Oldu odur dürr qıran, ləl əzən. (15;33)

It is difficult to understand the verse from this translation, which belongs to M. Zaki. The translator was so obsessed with keeping the rhythm that he did not take into account the many incomprehensible phrases and words in the text, and kept some phrases and word combinations as they were (i.e in Persian). This complicates the language of the text and creates difficulties for the reader. Below is S. Rustam's translation:

Dəlilik məlhəmilə ağıllanmazdı dəli,
Sındırmasa incini, əzib ovmasa ləli. (6;20)

(lit: A mad man would not become wise with the madness ointment, if he does not break a pearl).

The word that S. Rustam translates here as "dəlilik məlhəmi" (madness ointment) actually has a completely different meaning in Persian. In fact, the meaning of the word mufərrih that is pleasing, to give joy. (20;) As can be seen, both translations cause misunderstandings and difficulties for the reader who is not familiar with the classical text. What Nizami wanted to say in the verse was that if he had not broken the stone and precious ones, it would never have brought joy and happiness. That is, precious stones are always among ordinary stones.

A verse in the story "On the young prince and his old enemies" is given differently in the critical texts prepared by different researchers:

سر نکشد شاخ تو از سروبن
تا نرنی کردن شاخ کهن (22;176) behruz

Unlike Behruz Sarvatyan, A. Alizade, V. Dastgardi, Barat Zanjani, the phrase شاخ تو (sənin budağın - your branch) in the first line is marked as شاخ نو (yeni budaq - new branch). In translations (S. Rustam, X. Ulutürk) it has become our language like yeni budaq, too. S. Rustam translated this verse as follows:

Buda köhnə budağı, yeni pöhrə görərsən,

Təzə, cavan budaqdan təzə bəhrə görərsən.(6;126)
(lit: Prune the old branch, you will see new blossoms, you will see fresh fruit from a fresh, young branch)

As can be seen, S. Rustam tried to preserve the beauty of the meaning in order to increase the impact of the translation. In our opinion, this statement mentioned in the critical text prepared by Behruz Sarvatyan is wrong. Because the word نو i.e. "new" in the first line has been opposed by the word کهن i.e. "old" in the second line. Nizami has formed a contrast in this verse by creating parallels.

Even today, a number of differences of opinion still exist in various critical texts. In Iran, the critical text of Nizami Ganjavi's "Khamasa" has been repeatedly elaborated by several researchers. There are many differences between the critical texts prepared by V. Dastgardi, B. Zanjani, B. Sarvatyan, A. Alizade. Differences of opinion among commentators have also led to the diversity of texts.

We would like to draw attention to one more point. Below we present the conclusions reached by the researchers in a verse in the section on the praise of the Prophet:

بی قلم از پوست، برون خوان توی
بی سخن از مغز درون دان توی (22;30)

These verses are taken from the critical text compiled by V. Dastgerdi. Below is the conclusion reached by B. Sarvatyan:

با قلم از پوست، برون خوان توی
با خرد از مغز درون دان توی (22;59)

The version given by A. Alizade is different from these two:

با قلم از پوست برون خوان تری
با خرد از مغز درون دان تری (17;29)

First, let's explain the meaning of this verse. If we translate word by word, the verses sound like this. According to V. Dastgerdi: You read what is not written, you know what is not said. Without a doubt, you are the one who knows the inside of our brain.

In the text given by Sarvatyan, the meaning of this verse is as follows: You are the one who reads what is written with "pen" outside the skin. You are the one who knows the inside of people's brain with your mind. If we take a deeper and philosophical approach, we will see that these lines have a deeper meaning. Nizami Ganjavi proves that every verse and every line of his works benefited from the Quran, which he knew perfectly. The poet directly refers to the first verse of "Al-Qalam" surah of the Quran. (Nun. By the pen and that which they write!) (11);

In our opinion, the correct version is the text prepared by V. Dastgerdini. Because Allah knows what is not written. That is, He reads what is written even without a pen.

CONCLUSIONS

All these examples prove once again that the heritage of this genius poet should be re-examined and his works re-translated. Because Nizami Ganjavi's works contain a deeper and richer philosophy, and we

must pass on the essence of this philosophy to our days. The heritage of Nizami, which has been subjected to many distortions, should be given to the readers as it is, and the new generation should learn many things from the heritage of this genius poet. This poet, whose thoughts and actions are intertwined with Islam, has always been in search of justice. A fair society is the leading line in his works. It is important to reveal the main ideal of the poet's heritage by beginning re-translating and researching the works of the justice-loving poet.

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